

Studies on the Interaction of Lead and Zinc Ions with Ovalbumin by pH metric and Equilibrium Dialysis Methods

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The binding of lead(II) and zinc(II) to ovalbumin was studied by pH metric and equilibrium dialysis methods. The calculation of V_M was made by the difference of hydrogen ion dissociated from the protein in the presence and absence of the metal ions and these values were found to increase progressively with increase in the pH of the metal protein mixtures. The value of $\log K$ for metal carboxyl systems were found to be 1.84 and 1.94 for lead and zinc respectively, while for metal imidazole 2.38 and 3.04 for lead and zinc respectively. Zinc was also reported to react with lysine residues with a $\log K$ value of 3.68, while such studies were not possible for lead due to precipitation in the higher pH range. Comparison of $\log K$ values showed that binding with imidazole group was stronger than the carboxyl group. The standard free energy changes (ΔF°) of the combination were found to be -1.156 , -1.811 and -2.193 K cal/mole at pH , 5.50, 7.50 and 9.50 for zinc-ovalbumin whereas -1.096 and -1.418 at pH 5.50 and 6.80 for lead-ovalbumin systems. The result obtained from dialysis were considered more accurate than from pH metric, because the latter involved a comparison of the two curves in the absence and presence of the metal ions.

INTERACTION of metal ions with proteins and amino acids is of great importance on account of their high physiological activity. Some of them acts as biocatalyst, a few utilized for the building of tissue as well as in the transportation of biological fluids in the form of soluble complexes. A great many studies have been carried out the histidyl groups of the proteins, since this group is supposed to be responsible for most of the buffering power of proteins in the physiological pH range. Most of the work includes binding data with serum proteins employing different suitable techniques¹⁻⁵. Some work⁶⁻⁹ includes the interaction of metal ions with transfusin gelatin, soybean and α -casein, using different physico-chemical methods. A brief survey of the existing literature revealed that only a little work has been done on the binding of metal ions to ovalbumin, a protein of high biological significance, easily available in a well characterized form. Malik and Arora¹⁰ studied the binding of lead(II) and zinc(II) to this protein by applying polarographic method, the former showed weak combination with carboxyl and imidazole, while the latter revealed stronger combination with these groups as well as with lysine residues. The value of association constants were found to compare well with the similar groups of other proteins investigated by various workers.

It is well established that lead binds with amino acids, proteins and enzymes. The formation of lead-ovalbumin¹¹ and lead- γ -globulin complexes^{1,2} has served to fractionate serum proteins and even lead have been shown to inhibit most enzymes bearing a single functional $-SH$ groups. Based on the above

observations the interaction of lead(II) and zinc(II) with ovalbumin have been reported applying pH metric and equilibrium dialysis methods.

pH -metric method of determining binding is a rapid technique for the characterization of metal-protein systems. However, the result can not be so accurate because the calculation involves comparison of the titration curves. While equilibrium dialysis gives direct calculation of the binding data though it suffers from error due to Donnan equilibrium and adsorption of the ions on the dialysis membrane, the former may be avoided by using a large excess of the supporting electrolyte. From the value of V_M (mole metal ion bound per mole protein), the values of $\log K$ and standard free energy changes of combination for lead-ovalbumin and zinc-ovalbumin have been communicated.

Experimental

Ovalbumin (mol. wt. = 45,000) purchased from V. P. Chest Institute, Biochemical unit, New Delhi, 60 mg/ml was further purified by 80-100 saturation of ammonium sulphate using Lowery *et al.* method¹². The resulting mass was dissolved in about 25 ml of water and dialysed at 4° against distilled water in order to obtain an isoionic solution. The solution was centrifuged and stored in a pyrex stoppered flask. The concentration of the protein solution was determined by drying a known aliquot in an air oven at 105°. Since the solution was free from ions this was considered as a correct concentration of the sample. The purity was checked

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by determining the nitrogen content, which was found to be 15.86%. The number of ionisable groups determined from the titration data agree well with those obtained by the earlier workers^{1,4-15}.

Reagents :

Solution of lead nitrate and zinc nitrate (AnalaR) were prepared in doubly distilled water and estimated complexometrically with EDTA. 1.0 M potassium nitrate (BDH) was used for maintaining the ionic strengths (0.15).

Technique :

pH measurements : The pH measurement were made out on a cambridge bench pH meter with a glass electrode (least count 0.02 units). The pH meter was standardized with phthalate buffer (4.0) for acid range and with a borate buffer (9.20) for the alkaline range, respectively. Purified N₂ gas was passed through the mixture in the alkaline pH range.

Dialysis experiments : Cellophane bags prepared from commercial sausage casing (23/32 inch in diameter) were filled with a measured amount of protein solution (0.5%) and then immersed in a solution of Zn²⁺ or Pb²⁺ of known concentrations keeping ionic strength (0.15) same in both the solutions. All the bags were placed on a shaker at 30° for 72 hours, an interval sufficient for the attainment of equilibrium. The bags were removed and the external solution were analysed complexometrically with EDTA.

Procedure :

The following sets of solutions were prepared for pH metric titration :

(1) 1.0 ml of 6.0% ovalbumin was taken in different pyrex boiling tubes along with 1.5 ml of 1.0 M KNO₃ and different volumes of 0.0861 N HCl were added. The total volume was made 10.0. ml by adding requisite amount of double distilled water.

(2) 1.0 ml of 6.0% ovalbumin, 1.0 ml of 0.01 M Pb(II) or Zn(II) were mixed in different tubes along with 1.5 ml of the supporting electrolyte.

(3) Water and metal ions were similarly arranged in the absence of the protein.

Two similar sets were prepared, one for acid titration and other for alkali titration. The pH value of all the mixtures were determined after 24 hours of mixing.

In equilibrium dialysis two similar sets of solution were prepared for both the metal ions (0.30 × 10⁻³ M to 2.20 × 10⁻³ M) in different pyrex test-tubes

(5.0 ml) and 5.0 ml of protein filled in the dialysis bags at different pH values for the two systems. The ionic strength was kept 0.15, outside and inside by the addition of requisite amount of 1.0 M KNO₃.

Results and Discussion

The pH metric titrations of ovalbumin were carried out in order to determine the different number of ionisable groups and it was found that the equation¹⁶—

$$pH - \log \frac{\gamma_1}{n_1 - \gamma_1} = (PK_{int})_1 - 0.868 ZW$$

representing a titration curve for well known globular protein also gave the ionisable groups of ovalbumin^{1,4-15} in the absence of the metal ions. Since, in the presence of metal ions, a fraction of the acidic group will be removed from participation in hydrogen ion equilibria by metal binding, it was possible to calculate the binding data directly from the difference in H⁺ ion titration curves in the presence and absence of metal ion, just as in the case of Bjerrum's method¹⁷.

TABLE 1—BINDING DATA OF Zn(II) TO OVALBUMIN BY pH METRIC METHOD, CONCENTRATION OF Zn(NO₃)₂, 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, CONCENTRATION OF OVALBUMIN 0.111 × 10⁻³ M, IONIC STRENGTH = 0.15, TEMPERATURE = 25°C

pH	H ⁺ ions dissociated in the presence of Zn(II)	H ⁺ ions dissociated in the absence of Zn(II)	V _M	Log K	ΔF° K cal/mol
3.00	6.0	5.0	1.0	—	—
4.00	11.0	9.5	1.5	—	—
5.00	34	32	2.0	—	—
5.50	55	51.5	2.5	1.94	-1.156
6.50	65	61.5	3.5	—	—
7.50	70	65	5.0	3.04	-1.811
8.50	76.5	70	6.5	—	—
9.50	88	75.5	7.5	3.68	-2.193
10.50	91	83	8.0	—	—

The difference in pH with and without protein provided a way for determining bound H⁺ and OH⁻ ion with protein applying the equation of Cohn and Edsall¹⁸. From which the number of H⁺ ions dissociated per mole of ovalbumin (γ) were calculated in the presence and absence of the lead and zinc ions. Here the titration curve of protein with and without metal ions were quite different. Infact, the hydrogen ions dissociated per mole of protein were slightly greater in the presence of metal ions than the protein alone (Tables 1 and 2). This difference indicated that H⁺ ions were replaced by Pb(II) and Zn(II) ions. Thus the number of extra dissociated H⁺ ions in the presence of Pb(II) 0.001 M and Zn(II) 0.001 M would directly give moles of metal ions bound to per mole of ovalbumin (V_M).

The titration curve of zinc-ovalbumin covered wide pH range, hence calculations were made up to

TABLE 2—BINDING OF Pb(II) TO OVALBUMIN, CONCENTRATION $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, OVALBUMIN, CONCENTRATION $0.111 \times 10^{-3} M$, IONIC STRENGTH=0.15, TEMPERATURE=25°C

pH	H ⁺ ions dissociated in the presence of Pb(II)	H ⁺ ions dissociated in the absence of Pb(II)	V _M	Log K	ΔF° K cal/mol
3.00	6.0	5.0	1.0	—	—
4.00	11.0	9.5	1.5	—	—
5.00	34.0	32	2.0	—	—
5.50	53.9	51.5	2.4	1.84	-1.096
6.00	58.5	56.0	2.5	—	—
6.50	64.5	61.5	3.0	—	—
6.80	65.0	62.0	3.0	2.38	-1.418

pH 10.50, where all the C-amino groups of protein under went deprotonation. Since in lead-ovalbumin mixture precipitation of lead hydroxide occurred above pH 6.8, hence it was difficult to make any fair calculation for the C-amino groups of the lysine residues. It was found that both metals interacted with carboxyl and imidazolium groups of ovalbumin, since there was a progressive increase in the number of H⁺ ions dissociated at different pH values (Fig. 1a, b, c). The binding even started from pH 3.0, where a few carboxyl groups of the

Fig. 1. Plots of H⁺ ions dissociation per mole of ovalbumin vs pH for Zn²⁺ and Pb²⁺-ovalbumin systems. Curves (a)=ovalbumin, (b) Zn²⁺-ovalbumin and (c) Pb²⁺-ovalbumin systems respectively.

protein dissociated. The plots of V_M vs pH (Fig. 2a, b) revealed the increased binding with increased pH of the two systems. The data were theoretically in favour of the different ionisable group of protein as determined from the titration curve (Table 3). Moreover, the experimental data indicated that at extremely low pH (in absence and

Fig. 2. Plots of V_M vs pH for Zn²⁺ and Pb²⁺-ovalbumin systems.

presence of metal ions), the number of H⁺ ions bound were very high. This could be due to the increase in the radius of protein molecule, accompanied by penetration of protons and solvent molecules into the protein sphere thus altering the molecular size¹⁹.

The protein contained 53 carboxyl group, which started ionizing from pH 3.50, the metal ions were bound with the carboxylate residues. A lesser value of V_M at low pH could be explained by the fact that although all the carboxyl groups were fully deprotonated at pH 5.50 the positive locci on the protein molecule would contribute a repulsive electrostatic effect on the metal ions. On the other hand, a regular increase of V_M on alkaline side could be explained on the basis of the increase of the negative charge on the protein molecule. Moreover, the metal ions were bound to the histidyl and lysyl residues through co-ordination as with other protein. From the values of V_M and C_F (free metal ions) at any particular pH, the values of log k were calculated from Scatchard's equation²⁰ and reported in Table 4.

$$K = \frac{V_M}{(n - V_H^+ - V_M) C_F}$$

where V_H⁺ and V_M were the active sites covered by hydrogen ions and metal ions respectively, and n, the total number of such sites in the protein molecule. The results obtained confirmed the binding of zinc ions in the wide pH range while lead ions were found only in a narrow pH range.

Equilibrium dialysis :

More valuable information about the binding data has been obtained from equilibrium dialysis method. We consider the data of pH metry as approximate values because in it the calculation of V_M per protein molecule involved the difference

between two titration curves in the absence and presence of the metal ions. In these determinations we have assumed that the addition of KNO_3 does not bring any appreciable change in the isoionic pH of the protein. The supporting electrolyte does not affect the data obtained from equilibrium dialysis technique since it involved direct determination of binding data.

The V_M in this case also calculated as in the pH metric method. The results calculated at two different pH values are shown in Fig. 3. The binding has been shown to increase progressively with increase

Fig. 3. Plots of V_M vs $\log C_f$ for Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} -ovalbumin systems.

in the metal ion concentration and attained a limiting value at higher metal ion concentration. A comparison of V_M from two methods revealed a slightly lower value in case of equilibrium dialysis. The formation constants in both the case have been calculated from the Scatchard's equation as in the case of pH metric method.

Zinc-ovalbumin :

It is clear from the logarithmic plots (Fig. 3) that at pH 5.57 Zn^{2+} combined with the protein. Since at pH 5.57, all carboxyl groups from aspartate and glutamate residue were ionized and were thus available for binding with Zn ions. The value of $\log K$ for zinc-carboxyl system was found to be 1.94, exactly the same as determined by Malik and Arora¹⁰ using Polarographic method. The higher value of V_M at pH 7.50 was attributed to the interaction of zinc ions with the imidazole groups of histidyl residues. At pH 7.50 all the imidazole underwent deprotonation, hence became available for interaction with zinc ions. The observed higher value of $\log K$ (3.04) indicated a more stronger

binding of Zn^{2+} ions with imidazole than the carboxyl groups.

The highest value of $\log K$ for zinc and free imidazole was reported to be 2.80²¹ while the similar value for zinc-4-methyl imidazole was 2.98²². These studies with free and substituted imidazoles indicated that $\log K$ value increased with complexity of the molecule. The relatively high values of $\log K$ support the fact that under physiological conditions imidazole group of histidyl residues in protein were likely to be involved in the binding of zinc and other metal ions.

Gurd and Goodman²³ reported the $\log K$ value for zinc ions and histidine residues of human serum albumin to be 2.82. Evidence for this was given which was based on the number of zinc binding groups in the albumin molecule and on other grounds that these groups were imidazole of the histidine residue. The number of histidine groups in ovalbumin was just half of that in serum albumin when calculated from the same weight of each protein. The $\log K$ of 3.04 was calculated by subtracting V_M at pH 5.57 from V_M at pH 7.50 at the same total metal ion concentration. Our value of $\log K$ (3.04) appears to be correct since approximately same $\log K$ value (3.02) was obtained from polarographic method¹⁰. The present value varied by $\pm 0.6\%$ and these are comparable with those obtained by earlier method.

The maximum number of imidazole sites involved was found to be 4 from the logarithmic and reciprocal plots (Figs. 3 and 4). It appeared that the combination was 1 : 1. The constancy of $\log K$ is a proof that only imidazole groups are involved in the reaction. Our value of $\log K$ (3.04)

Fig. 4. Plots of $\frac{1}{V_M}$ vs $\frac{1}{C_f}$ for Zn^{2+} -ovalbumin system.

is just half to that of zinc-insulin ($\log K=6.0$), where each Zn^{2+} is shown to react with two imidazole group instead of one, at least when the zinc concentration was low. Thus in ovalbumin the combination of zinc to imidazole is 1 : 1, which has also been supported by pH metric data. Zinc also reacted with the C-ammonium groups of the lysyl residues as obtained from pH metric data. The $\log K$ value was found to be 3.68. Thus the reactivity of zinc ions to different group of ovalbumin was found in the order carboxyl < imidazole < C-ammonium.

Lead-ovalbumin :

Equilibrium dialysis between lead and protein provides sufficient evidence for its interaction with the carboxyl and imidazole groups of ovalbumin. The value of V_M at both pH values (5.57 and 6.50) rises progressively with increase in metal ion concentration but tend to attain a limiting value at higher metal ion concentration (Fig. 3 and 5). The $\log K$ values (1.84) for lead-carboxyl system have been found to be approximately constant over a wide range of metal ion concentration. However, the $\log K$ value is much less than the logarithm of the first association constant of lead acetate complex (2.7). In view of the competition which exists between the nitrate ion of supporting electrolyte such behaviour is not unlikely. The actual concentration of carboxylate residues was $0.0069M$ in $1.333 \times 10^{-4}M$ protein, whereas the concentration of KNO_3 was $0.15M$ since lead under went complexation with nitrate ion ($\log K$ 1.1). It may be assumed that such competition exists between carboxylate residues and nitrate ions of the supporting electrolyte.

At pH 6.50, the imidazole groups of the histidine offers sites for binding the lead ions, the $\log K$ value

Fig. 5. Plots of $\frac{1}{V_M}$ vs $\frac{1}{C_f}$ for Pb^{2+} -ovalbumin system.

for this combination was found to be 2.38. Approximately 2 imidazole sites per mole of ovalbumin were covered by lead while 4 by the zinc ions, most probably, also lead-imidazole ratio is 1 : 1, this is also supported—

TABLE 3—IONISABLE GROUPS OF OVALBUMIN (45,000)

Groups	No. in the titration, ionic strength 0.033	Number from present curve (0.15, ionic strength)
Carboxyl	52	53
Imidazolium	7	8
Amino	20	22
Total cationic	40	45
Guanidinium	13	15
		(by difference)

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF Log K VALUES OF ZINC AND LEAD FOR OVALBUMIN AND DIFFERENT SYSTEMS

Ligand	Technique	Log K carboxyl		Log K imidazole		Log K amino group	
		Zn(II)	Pb(II)	Zn(II)	Pb(II)	Zn(II)	Pb(II)
Ovalbumin	pH metry	1.94 ^p	1.84 ^p	3.04 ^p	2.38 ^p	3.68 ^p	—
	Polarography	1.92 ^a	1.84 ^a	3.02 ^a	2.28 ^a	3.68 ^a	—
	Equilibrium dialysis	1.34 ^p	1.84 ^p	3.04 ^p	2.38 ^p	—	—
Transturian	Equilibrium dialysis	1.87 ^b	1.84 ^c	2.912 ^b	2.21 ^c	—	—
	Polarography	—	1.81 ^d	—	—	—	—
	pH metry	1.87 ^c	2.00 ^d	2.74 ^e	—	—	—
Bovine serum albumin	Polarography	—	—	2.90 ^f	2.30 ^f	—	—
Guanidate Human serum albumin	Equilibrium dialysis	—	—	2.69 ^g	—	—	—
Human serum albumin	—do—	—	—	2.82 ^h	—	—	—
Insulin	Polarography	—	—	3.00 ⁱ	—	—	—
Soybean	pH metry	1.90 ^j	—	2.77 ^j	—	—	—
Acetate	—	1.08 ^k	2.71 ^l	—	—	—	—
Imidazole	pH metry	—	—	2.80 ^m	—	—	—
4-methyl imidazole	—do—	—	—	2.98 ⁿ	—	—	—

P—Present studies, a—ref. 10, b=25, c=9, d=6, e=26, f=2, g=27, h=23, i=3, j=28, k=29, l=17, m=21, n=22.

by pH metric data. The low value of log K for lead-ovalbumin than lead-histidine amino acid (6.84) accounted the lesser availability of this group in the protein molecule. It was not possible to carry out dialysis studies at higher pH values on account of the precipitation of lead hydroxide.

The standard free energy changes of these interactions were calculated by the following relation :

$$\Delta F^\circ = -2.303 RT \log K$$

These being -1.156, -1.811 and -2.193, K cal/mole of the binding sites at pH, 5.50, 7.50 and 9.50, respectively for zinc ions, while for lead-ovalbumin system the ΔF° being -1.096 and -1.418, at pH 5.50 and 6.50, respectively. The order of combination of these metal ions with the carboxyl and with imidazole groups of ovalbumin was Zn(II) > Pb(II) which was exactly the same as was found by Irving and William²⁴ for these metals in complexes with 8-hydroxy quinoline and dithiozone, both of which, like imidazole group contained secondary and tertiary nitrogen atoms. A comparison of log K values obtained by us with those obtained by other workers using different methods for the binding of Pb(II) and Zn(II) with ovalbumin and other proteins is made in the Table 4.

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